
CROSS-COMPANY FINANCING AND ACQUISITIONS

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ABSTRACT

The definition of "Loan and Investment by Corporation" has changed because of the 2013 Companies Act (Act). According to the new Legislation, investments between corporations may only be done through two investment entities. Subject to limitations, which include firms formed outside of India, the 2013 Act says that companies can only make investments through two tiers of investment companies. Such limitations are not currently in place because of the 1956 Act. Additionally, under the 2013 Act, a holding company's loans or investments in a subsidiary firm are no longer immune from the restrictions of section 372A of the 1956 Act, which had been available to private companies. A Business must invest through no more than two layers of investment firms in accordance with Section 186(1) of the Act. According to Section 2(87) of the Act's explanation (d), "Layer" refers to a holding company's subsidiary or subsidiaries. A company whose primary activity is the acquisition of shares, debentures, or other securities is referred to as a "investment company." The following situations are exempt from Section 186 (1)'s provisions: If a firm buys a company that was founded outside of India and that company has investment subsidiaries that are more than two layers deep according to the rules of that nation. A subsidiary firm is prohibited from having any investing subsidiaries to comply with any legislation, rule, or regulation that is now in effect.²

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² <https://www.jstor.org/stable/439504806>

I. RESTRICTIONS ON LOAN & GUARANTEE AND INTEREST RATE

A business cannot provide any inter-corporate loans, guarantees, or securities if interest payments are past due. This restriction will last until the business has fully fixed the default. Additionally, a firm is not permitted to invest through two layers of investment companies, with a few exceptions, to mitigate financial risks associated with complex investment structures.

Loans should not be made available at interest rates lower than the current yield of the government security with the term closest to the loan's duration, whether it is one year, three years, five years, or more. However, when a loan is issued for industrial R&D projects and the government controls 26% or more of the paid-up capital, this regulation does not apply, thus fostering investment in strategic sectors while ensuring prudent financial management.

II. APPROVAL FROM MEMBERS [SECTION 186(3)]

Though the Section 186(2) makes restriction as above, Section 186(3), empowers a Company to give loan, guarantee or provide any security or acquisition beyond the limit but subject to prior approval of members by a special resolution passed at a general meeting.³

III. DISCLOSURE NECESSARY FOR INTER CORPORATE LOANS AND INVESTMENTS

The following information must be disclosed to shareholders in the financial statements if an inter-corporate loan or investment is made:

- The number of loans offered, the investment made, the guarantee offered, and the security offered.
- The order to supply the same.
- The recipient recommended using the same.⁴

IV. APPROVAL OF BOARD AND PUBLIC FINANCIAL INSTITUTION [SECTION 185(5)]

³https://www.icsi.edu/media/filer_public/28/5d/285d5241-fb04-4e18-8e6c-6c70a6b05f83/loans_guarantees_securities_and_investments_in_securities_-cs_dr_dk_jain.pdf

⁴ https://www.mca.gov.in/Ministry/notification/pdf/AS_18.pdf

In pursuant to provisions of Section 186(5) of the Act, every company shall take consent of all the directors present at the board meeting before making any investment, giving loan and guarantee, and providing security. In case of company has already taken loan etc., from any Public Financial Institutions, then it is mandatory to take prior approval from such Public Financial Institution.⁵

V. RATE OF INTEREST ON INTER-CORPORATE LOANS

A company cannot give an inter-corporate loan at a rate of interest lower than the prevailing yield of one, three, five or ten years of government security closest to the loan term.

VI. REGISTER OF LOAN [SECTION 186 (9 AND 10)]

Every Corporation is required by Section 186(9) of the Act to keep a register that details any loans, guarantees, securities, or investments that have been made. Every company that provides a loan, a guarantee, a security, or acquires securities must, starting from the date of formation, keep a register in Form MBP 2 and enter, separately, the specifics of each loan and guarantee provided, security provided, and acquisition completed as noted.

This register must be kept at the company's registered office and in the custody of the company secretary or another individual designated by the Board for this purpose. It must also be preserved forever.

VII. NON-APPLICABILITY OF SECTION 186:

The Section 186 (except Sub Section 1) of the Companies Act, 2013 does not apply to the following:

- (a) to a loan made, guarantee given, or security provided by a banking company or an insurance company or a housing finance company in the ordinary course of its business or a company engaged in the business of financing of companies or of providing infrastructural facilities;
- (b) to any acquisition—
 - (i) made by a non-banking financial company registered under Chapter IIIB of the Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934 and whose principal business is acquisition of securities:

⁵ <https://wirc-icai.org/wirc-reference-manual/part5/loans-to-and-by-companies-sections-185-and-186>

Provided that exemption to non-banking financial company shall be in respect of its investment and lending activities.

- (ii) made by a company whose principal business is the acquisition of securities.
- (iii) of shares allotted in pursuance of clause (a) of sub-section (1) of section 62.

VIII. PENALTY FOR CONTRAVENTION OF SECTION 186:

For Company:

Every Company which contravenes the provisions of this Section shall be liable to a penalty which shall not be less than Rupees twenty-five thousand, but which may extend to Rupees five lakhs.

For Officers:

Every officer of the Company who is in default shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to two years and fine which shall not be less than Rupees twenty-five thousand, but which may extend to Rupees One lakh.⁶

IX. PROCEDURES INVOLVED IN MAKING LOAN, GIVING GUARANTEE AND PROVIDING SECURITY

A company can give any loan or give any guarantee or provide security and acquire securities of any Body corporate through Board resolution. No investment shall be made or loan or guarantee or security given by the company unless the resolution sanctioning it is passed at a meeting of the Board with the consent of all the directors present at the meeting. For specimen of Board resolution, please refer Annexure-II and III given at the end of this chapter. It is to be kept in mind that a company can give any loan or give any guarantee or provide security and acquire securities of any Body corporate through Board resolution up to 60% of its paid-up capital, free reserves, and security premium account or 100% of its free reserves and security premium whichever is more.

Based on the aforesaid conditions and requirements of the company meeting of Board of Directors is to be convened after giving proper notice and proposals of giving loan or giving guarantee or providing security etc. are to be discussed.³ Board may approve a loan,

⁶ <https://corpbiz.io/learning/loan-and-investment-by-company-section-186/>

investment, guarantee, and security proposed within the limits of section 186(2) of the Companies (Registration of offices and fees) Rules, 2014 if there is no default in repayment of loan or interest thereon to the Public Financials Institution. 60% of its paid-up capital, free reserves, security premium account or 100% of reserves and security premium whichever is more can be approved by the Board. Registers are to be maintained in Form MBP-2 by every company giving loan or giving guarantee or providing security or making an acquisition, from the date of its registration and the particulars of loan and guarantee given, securities provided and acquisition entered therein. No loan shall be given at a rate of interest below the prevailing yield of one year, three years, five year or ten-year Government security closest to the tenor of the loan.

Company must disclose details of loans, guarantees, and security to members, and scrutinize repayment history to ensure no default is subsisting.⁷

X. CONCLUSION

- This rule does not apply when a loan is given out for industrial R&D projects when the government owns 26 percent or more of the paid-up capital.
- Pace of Revenue on Between Corporate Credits An organization can't give a between corporate advance at a pace of interest lower than the overarching yield of one, three, five or a decade of government security nearest to the credit term.
- Section 186's inapplicability: The following are exempt from the Companies Act of 2013's Section 186 (with the exception of Subsection 1): a) to a loan, guarantee, or security provided in the normal course of business by a housing finance company, insurance company, banking company, or company involved in financing companies or providing infrastructure facilities; (b) to any acquisition (i) made by a non-banking financial company whose primary business is the acquisition of securities and registered under Chapter IIIB of the Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934: With the exception of non-banking financial institutions for their investment and lending activities; ii) made by an organization whose main business is buying securities; (iii) of the shares distributed in accordance with clause (a) of paragraph (1) of section 62.

References

⁷ <https://www.corporatelaws.in/2017/01/Procedure-Inter-Corporate-Loans-and-Investments.html>

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